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Reggio Emilia Approach in Early Childhood Education and Preschoolers' Academic Performance in Literacy Skills in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District

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Abstract

This study investigates the effect of Reggio Emilia approach on preschoolers' academic performance in literacy skills in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District. Four research questions and four null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The study adopted a quasi-experimental control group research design. The population of the study comprised all the 15,628 nursery two preschoolers from the 385 public primary schools with early childhood education classes in the study area. A sample size of 156 nursery two preschoolers was selected for the study using multistage sampling technique. The study had four intact classes of experimental groups and one intact class of a constant control group. The instrument for data collection was Literacy Skills Performance Test (LSPT). The instrument was validated by three experts and subjected to a reliability test using Kuder Richardson's formula, and a reliability coefficient of 0.85 was obtained. The test instrument was marked over 100%. The data generated were analysed using mean and standard deviation for answering the research questions, while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Results of the study revealed that Reggio Emilia approach had a significant effect on the academic performance of nursery two preschoolers in literacy skills. Preschoolers who were taught literacy skills using Reggio Emilia approach had higher mean scores than their counterparts taught using the conventional approach. It was recommended, among others, that Reggio Emilia approach should be adopted as one of the teaching methods in implementing the early childhood curriculum, and the government, through the Universal Basic Education Board, should train all the early childhood education teachers in the Reggio Emilia approach.

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Keywords: Reggio Emilia approach, literacy skills, early childhood education, preschoolers, academic performance

Introduction

Early childhood education in Nigeria plays a crucial role in a child's formative years. It is about honing and moulding the holistic child. A child's early years lay the foundation for cognitive, physical, and emotional development. It is at this stage that children need to learn and develop their literacy skills. The National Policy on Education (2014) defines early childhood education as providing education in an educational institution to children aged three–five years before they enter primary school. Ranweiler (2017) opined that children's brains develop faster between the ages of zero and three and are like sponges, absorbing information and making connections at a rapid pace. Because of this, it is pertinent to foster literacy skills during the early stages of life, as benefits of early literacy extend well beyond the early years.

Research has shown that children who develop strong literacy skills in their early childhood are more likely to succeed academically throughout their schooling years. They have better language acquisition and critical thinking abilities and are more confident in expressing themselves. Furthermore, a solid foundation in literacy sets the stage for lifelong learning and enhances overall literacy proficiency (Tamis-Lemonde and Rodriguez, 2018). Literacy skills are vital to the overall development of children. Literacy skills are not just limited to reading and writing; they encompass the ability to comprehend and communicate effectively. Literacy is the ability to read, write, speak, and listen in a way that enables us to communicate effectively and make sense of the world. Literacy is the foundation for reading, writing, communicating, and socializing. Children develop literacy skills early through exposure to language, printed materials, and meaningful interactions.

According to Castle (2013), the key components of early childhood literacy skills are: language development and vocabulary acquisition; print awareness and alphabet knowledge; knowledge of the names and sounds associated with printed letters; phonological awareness (the ability to detect, manipulate, or analyse the auditory aspects of spoken language (including the ability to distinguish or segment words, syllables, or phonemes); rapid automatic naming of letters or digits; rapid automatic naming of objects or colours; the ability to write letters; and concepts about

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print knowledge (example, left-right, front-back). UNICEF's (2022) report on foundational literacy and numeracy in basic education in Nigeria highlighted that 70 percent of children in Nigeria cannot read with meaning or solve simple math problems, and only 49 percent and 55 percent of children in school achieve basic proficiency in literacy and numeracy, respectively.

Despite the importance of literacy skills, there are observable problems associated with their teaching and learning, especially at the early childhood level of education. These problems include poor methods of teaching. This is supported by the assertion of Agommuoh and Nzewi (2023) that attributed the deterioration in pupils' achievement in literacy skills to ineffective methods of teaching. The common method of teaching, especially in public schools, is learning by rote or recitation in unison. Most teachers teach with cane in their hands to enforce discipline and with a stroke on the head of any child who misbehaves or fails to chorus any recitation properly. Consequently, children listen in fear and cannot concentrate for effective learning to occur. This deplorable situation has led to researchers calling for urgent intervention through the use of play-based, child-centred interactive approaches to see if there will be improvement in the learning outcomes of early childhood education children. One of such approach is the Reggio Emilia approach.

Birinci (2017) reported that Reggio Emilia approach has helped children to express themselves in endless ways, making use of various senses. Unamba, Ugochukwu and Udeji (2022) assessed the impact of Reggio Emilia instructional approach in enhancing critical thinking skills and academic achievement of pupils in mathematics in Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education in Owerri Municipal Council Area of Imo State. The result of the study showed that the implementation of Reggio Emilia instructional approach is an effective method of developing pupils' critical thinking skills and academic achievement in mathematics, irrespective of their gender. Elui and Ogoru (2021) investigated the impact of Reggio Emilia approach on nursery three children's interest and achievement in emergent literacy. Results of the study revealed that Reggio Emilia approach had significant effects on the achievement and interest of nursery three children in emergent literacy.

The Reggio Emilia approach is an educational philosophy and pedagogy focused on preschool and primary education. This approach is a learner-centered and constructivist self-guided curriculum that uses self-directed, experiential learning in

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relationship-driven environments. The approach is based on the principles of respect, responsibility and community through exploration, discovery and play. At the core of this philosophy is an assumption that children form their own personality during the early years of development and that they are endowed with "a hundred languages", through which they can express their ideas. This approach was developed after World War II by Pedagogist Loris Malaguzzi and parents in the villages around Reggio Emilia, Italy (Cadwell, 2018).

Ayla (2014) opined that Reggio Emilia philosophy is based upon the principle that children must have some control over the direction of their learning; children must be able to learn through experiences of touching, moving, listening, and observing. The Reggio Emilia approach to early education reflects a theoretical kinship with John Dewey, Jean Piaget, Lev Vygotsky and Jerome Bruner, among others. Parents are vital components to the Reggio Emilia philosophy; they are viewed as partners, collaborators, and advocates for their children. Teachers respect parents as each child's first teacher and involve parents in every aspect of the curriculum. Parents are expected to take part in discussions about school policy, child development concerns, and curriculum planning and evaluation.

In the Reggio approach, the teacher is considered a co-learner and collaborator with the child and not just an instructor. Teachers are encouraged to facilitate the child's learning by planning circle time activities and lessons based on the child's interests, asking questions to further understanding, and actively engaging in the activities alongside the child, instead of passively observing the child learning (Hewett, 2021). Malaguzzi believed that the physical environment is of fundamental importance to the early childhood programme, referring to it as the "third teacher". Reggio Emilia approach has seven learning/activities areas in the classroom (cognitive/mental, creativity, construction, home pretend, language, sensory and STEM) and these areas/activities promote learning in the six domains: physical domain, socio and emotional domain, cognitive domain, creative art, language development domain, national values, respect and diversity (Inan, 2021).

The purpose of this study therefore, was to determine the effect of Reggio Emilia approach on preschoolers' academic performance in literacy skills in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District. Specifically, the study sought to ascertain:

- i. the difference in the mean scores of preschoolers taught reading skills using Reggio Emilia approach and those taught using the conventional approach;
- ii. the difference in the mean scores of preschoolers taught writing skills using Reggio Emilia approach and those taught using the conventional approach;
- iii. the difference in the mean scores of preschoolers taught speaking skills using Reggio Emilia approach and those taught using the conventional approach.
- iv. the difference in the mean scores of preschoolers taught listening skills using Reggio Emilia approach and those taught using the conventional approach.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- I. What is the difference in the mean scores of preschoolers taught reading skills using Reggio Emilia approach and those taught using the conventional approach?
- ii. What is the difference in the mean scores of preschoolers taught writing skills using Reggio Emilia approach and those taught using the conventional approach?
- iii. What is the difference in the mean scores of preschoolers taught speaking skills using Reggio Emilia approach and those taught using the conventional approach?
- iv. What is the difference in the mean scores of preschoolers taught listening skills using Reggio Emilia approach and those taught using the conventional approach?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance:

- Ho₁:** There is no significant difference in the mean scores of preschoolers taught reading skills using Reggio Emilia approach and those taught using the conventional approach.
- Ho₂:** There is no significant difference in the mean scores of preschoolers taught writing skills using Reggio Emilia approach and those taught using the conventional approach.
- Ho₃:** There is no significant difference in the mean scores of preschoolers taught speaking skills using Reggio Emilia approach and those taught using the conventional approach.
- Ho₄:** There is no significant difference in the mean scores of preschoolers taught listening skills using Reggio Emilia approach and those taught using the conventional approach.

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Methodology

This study adopted a quasi-experimental control group research design. This research design was adopted because it could reveal whether or not a particular instructional approach is better than the other, and can also identify differences in the performance (scores) of the two groups (experimental and control group). The study was carried out in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District. The population consisted of all the 15,628 nursery two preschoolers from the 385 Public primary schools with ECCE classes in the area of study. A sample size of 156 nursery two preschoolers was selected for the study using a multistage sampling technique.

At stage one, the nine Local Government Areas in the study area were clustered into one. At stage two, five public schools with early childhood education classes were randomly selected from five Local Government Areas. At stage three, the selected schools were purposively divided into four intact classes of experimental groups and one intact class of constant control group. The experimental groups were taught literacy skills (reading, writing, speaking, and listening) using Reggio Emilia approach while the control group were also taught same concept but using the conventional approach.

The instrument for data collection was the researchers' developed test instrument titled: Literacy Skills Performance Test (LSPT). The LSPT consisted of forty multiple-choice items testing preschoolers reading, writing, speaking and listening skills. The instrument was validated by experts in early childhood education and educational research. The validated instrument was subjected to a field trial to confirm its appropriateness. The reliability of the instrument was obtained through a test-retest method with 50 preschoolers who were not part of the study sample. The data obtained were analysed using Kuder Richardson 20 formula and reliability co-efficient of 0.85 was obtained. The experiment lasted for 3 weeks, pretest was given before the treatment and after treatment, a post-test was given using the re-arranged version of the LSPT. The test instruments were marked over 100%. The data generated were analysed using mean and standard deviation for answering the research questions while the Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significant.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the difference in the mean scores of preschoolers taught reading skills using Reggio Emilia approach and those taught using the conventional approach?

Table 1: Difference in the mean scores of preschoolers taught reading skills using Reggio Emilia approach and those taught using the conventional approach

Group	Pre-test scores				Post test scores			
	N	\bar{x}	SD	MD	N	\bar{x}	SD	MD
Reggio Emilia Approach	34	30.4	4.8		34	82.7	11.5	
Conventional Approach	32	29.8	7.4	0.6	32	68.5	9.6	14.2
Total	66	30.1	6.1		66	75.6	12.5	

Source: Field Data (2024)

Data in Table 1 indicates that preschoolers taught reading skills using Reggio Emilia approach had higher mean performance score of 82.7 and standard deviation of 11.5, than preschoolers taught using the conventional approach with the mean performance score of 68.5 and standard deviation of 9.6. The mean difference was 14.2. This result proves that Reggio Emilia approach has a positive effect on preschoolers' academic performance in literacy skills (reading skills).

Hypothesis 1

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of preschoolers taught reading skills using Reggio Emilia approach and those taught using the conventional approach.

Table 2: Summary of the Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) in the mean scores of preschoolers taught reading skills using Reggio Emilia approach and those taught using the conventional approach.

Source of variation	Type III sum of square	DF	Mean square	F	P. Value
Corrected model	5504.988	2	2752.492	35.078	.000
Intercept	4954.390	1	4954.390	63.139	.000
Pretest scores	1962.074	1	1962.074	25.005	.000
Groups	3411.025	1	3411.025	43.470	.000
Error	5257.355	63	78.468		
Total	411140.00	66			
Corrected total	10762.343	65			

a.R squared = .512 (adjusted R. squared = .497)

Significant at .05 alpha level.

Source: Field Data (2024)

Data in Table 2 show the calculated F-Value of 43.470 and the probability value of .000 in respect of the treatment for the two groups. Since the P-value = .000 was less than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected; hence, there was a statistical significant difference in the mean scores of preschoolers taught reading skills using Reggio Emilia approach and those taught using the conventional approach.

Research Question 2

What is the difference in the mean scores of preschoolers taught writing skills using Reggio Emilia approach and those taught using the conventional approach?

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Table 3: Difference in the mean scores of preschoolers taught writing skills using Reggio Emilia approach and those taught using the conventional approach

Group	Pre-test scores				Post test scores			
	N	\bar{x}	SD	MD	N	\bar{x}	SD	MD
Reggio Emilia approach	33	41.0	5.9		33	98.5	10.9	
Conventional approach	32	40.9	7.2	0.1	32	68.5	9.10	10.0
Total	65	41.0	6.6		65	73.5	11.1	

Source: Field Data (2024)

As shown in Table 3, the post-test mean performance scores of preschoolers taught writing skills using Reggio Emilia approach ($\bar{x}=78.5$) is greater than the mean scores performance of those taught using the conventional approach ($\bar{x}=68.5$) with a mean difference of 10.0. This further proved that Reggio Emilia approach has a positive effect on preschoolers' academic performance in literacy skills (writing skills).

Hypothesis 2

Ho₂: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of preschoolers taught writing skills using Reggio Emilia approach and those taught using the conventional approach.

Table 4: Summary of the Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) in the mean scores of preschoolers taught writing skills using Reggio Emilia approach and those taught using the conventional approach.

Source of variation	Type III sum of square	DF	Mean square	F	P. Value
Corrected model	4380.239	2	2190119	35.536	.000
Intercept	3687.259	1	3687.259	59.828	.000
Pretest scores	2650.181	1	2650.181	43.001	.000
Groups	1654.718	1	1654.718	26.830	.000
Error	4129.247	62	61631		
Total	386520.000	65			
Corrected total	8509.486	64			

a.R squared = .515 (Adjusted R. squared = .500*Significant at .05 level alpha level.

Source: Field Data (2024)

The result as presented in Table 4 shows the calculated F-value of 26.849 and the probability value of .000 for the two groups. Since the P-value (-.000) was less than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. Hence there was a statistical significant difference in the mean scores of preschoolers taught reading skills using Reggio Emilia approach and those taught using the conventional approach.

Research Question 3

What is the difference in the mean scores of preschoolers taught speaking skills using Reggio Emilia approach and those taught using the conventional approach?

Table 5: Difference in the mean scores of preschoolers taught speaking skills using Reggio Emilia approach and those taught using the conventional approach

Group	Pre-test scores				Post test scores			
	N	x	SD	MD	N	x	SD	MD
Reggio Emilia approach	21	42.5	5.7		21	77.0	11.8	
				0.7				8.5
Conventional approach	32	43.2	6.3		32	68.5	9.01	
Total	53	42.9	6.0		53	72.8	11.5	

Source: Field Data (2024)

The result in Table 5 shows the mean scores and standard deviation of the experimental and control group. Preschoolers that were taught speaking skills using Reggio Emilia approach had higher post-test mean score of (\bar{x}) 77.0 and standard deviation (SD) of 11.8 than preschoolers taught using the conventional approach with a mean score performance of (\bar{x}) 68.5 and standard deviation (SD) of 9.01. The mean difference was 8.5. This proves that Reggio Emilia approach has positive effect on preschoolers' academic performance in literacy skills (speaking skills).

Hypothesis 3

Ho₃: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of preschoolers taught speaking skills using Reggio Emilia approach and those taught using the conventional approach.

Table 6: Summary of the Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) in the mean scores of preschoolers taught speaking skills using Reggio Emilia approach and those taught using the conventional approach.

Source of variation	Type III sum of square	DF	Mean square	F	P. Value
Corrected model	7304.77	2	3652.39	169.75	.000
Intercept	1571.4212	1	1571.442	73.04	.000
Pretest scores	6036.145	1	6036.145	280.343	.000
Groups	1195.181	1	1195.181	55.549	.000
Error	1441.570	50	21.56		
Total	379444000	53			
Corrected total	8746.343	52			

a.R squared = .835 (Adjusted R. squared = .830)* Significant at .05 level alpha level.

Source: Field Data (2024)

The result as presented in Table 6 shows the calculated F-Value of 55.549 and the probability value of .000 for the groups. Since the P-value (.000) was less than 0.05 level of significance at the degrees of freedom 1 and 50, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that there was a significant difference in the mean scores of preschoolers taught speaking skills using Reggio Emilia approach and those taught using the conventional approach.

Research Question 4

What is the difference in the mean scores of preschoolers taught listening skills using Reggio Emilia approach and those taught using the conventional approach?

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Table 7: Difference in the mean scores of preschoolers taught listening skills using Reggio Emilia approach and those taught using the conventional approach

Group	Pre-test scores				Post test scores			
	N	x	SD	MD	N	x	SD	MD
Reggio Emilia approach	30	38.1	6.5		30	83.8	11.2	
Conventional approach	32	37.9	7.2	0.2	32	68.5	9.01	15.3
Total	62	38.0	6.9		62	76.2	12.7	

Source: Field Data (2024)

The result in Table 7 shows that the post-test mean performance scores (\bar{x} = 83.8, SD = 11.2) of preschoolers taught listening skills using Reggio Emilia approach was higher than those taught using the conventional approach with a mean difference of 15.3. This affirms that Reggio Emilia approach has an effect on preschoolers' academic performance in literacy skills (listening skills).

Hypothesis 4

Ho₄: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of preschoolers taught listening skills using Reggio Emilia approach and those taught using the conventional approach.

Table 8: Summary of the Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) in the mean scores of preschoolers taught listening skills using Reggio Emilia approach and those taught using the conventional approach.

Source of variation	Type III sum of square	DF	Mean square	F	P. Value
Corrected model	6878.334	2	3439.167	54.189	.000
Intercept	4134.443	1	4134.443	65.144	.000
Pretest scores	2804.676	1	2804.676	44.192	.000
Groups	3836.431	1	3836.431	60.448	.000
Error	4252.238	59	63.466		
Total	416972.000	62			
Corrected total	11130.572	61			

a.R squared = .618 (Adjusted R. squared = .607)* Significant at .05 level alpha level.

Source: Field Data (2024)

The result presented in Table 8 shows the calculated F-value of 60.448 and the probability value of .000 for the groups. Since the P-value of .000 was less than the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. Hence there was a significant difference in the mean scores of preschoolers taught listening skills using Reggio Emilia approach and those taught using the conventional approach.

Summary of Findings

The findings of the study are summarised as follows:

1. There is a significant difference between the mean scores of nursery two preschoolers taught literacy skills (reading skills, writing skills, speaking skills and listening skills) using Reggio Emilia approach and those taught using the conventional approach.
2. Nursery two preschoolers who were taught literacy skills (reading skills, writing skills, speaking skills and listening skills) using Reggio Emilia approach had higher mean scores than their counterparts taught using the conventional approach.
3. Reggio Emilia approach has a positive significant effect on preschoolers' academic performance in literacy skills (reading skills, writing skills, speaking skills and listening skills).

Discussion of findings

The findings of this study revealed that there is a significant difference in the mean score of nursery two preschoolers taught literacy skills using Reggio Emilia approach and those taught using the conventional approach. Preschoolers taught using Reggio Emilia approach had higher mean scores in their academic performance in literacy skills than their counterparts taught using the conventional approach. The findings confirmed that of Inan (2021), who found out that Reggio Emilia approach inspired preschoolers to successfully accomplished healthy literacy development. Reggio Emilia approach has an environment with learning areas/ activities that can support the learning and development of literary skills among nursery school children.

Children exposed to Reggio Emilia approach are given a rich and playful environment that satisfies interest and triggers their learning (Inan, 2019). The circle time activities such as games, storytelling, recitation of rhymes, pretend/role play and many more enhance pupils listening skills, speaking skills, writing skills and reading skills. The preschoolers' higher academic performance after being exposed to Reggio Emilia approach could be attributed to these rich and playful environments. The children had opportunities to participate actively in literacy activities as each of them pursued their varying interests under the guidance of their teachers.

Results in tables 1 and 2 showed that preschoolers exposed to Reggio Emilia approach had higher mean scores in reading skills than those exposed to conventional approach with a mean difference of 14.2. This finding is in consonance with the findings of Nair, Yusof and Arumugam (2014), who found that the Reggio Emilia approach helped to arouse the children's interest in learning reading. Through rhyming, games, singing songs, and playing with words, children can develop their phonemic awareness and lay a strong foundation for future literacy skills. Additionally, reading aloud and storytelling during the circle time expands preschoolers' vocabulary, and enhances their listening skills.

The results in Tables 3 and 4 revealed that preschoolers taught writing skills using Reggio Emilia approach had higher mean scores than those taught using the conventional approach with a mean difference of 10.0. The reason for the difference could be attributed to the fact that Reggio Emilia classroom environment provides preschoolers with diverse manipulating materials that could enhance their fine motor skills which are basic prerequisite for hand writing development. This result is in accord

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with the findings of Arzu and Mubeccel (2015) which showed that the use of Reggio Emilia approach enhanced handwriting development process among the children.

Also, the results in Tables 5 and 6 and Tables 7 and 8 indicated a significant difference between the mean scores of preschoolers taught speaking and listening skills using Reggio Emilia approach and those taught using the conventional approach. Preschoolers taught speaking and listening skills using Reggio Emilia had higher mean scores than their counterparts with a mean difference of 8.5 and 15.3, respectively. This success could be attributed to the fact that Reggio Emilia classrooms are organised into defined learning areas such as cognitive/mental area, creativity area, construction area, home pretend area, language area, sensory area, science, technology, engineering and mathematics area.

In the learning areas, materials such as books, letters, toys, local materials, pictures, print, names, writing tools, paint, construction materials, animal's model, numbers cards, alphabet flash cards and many more are kept for pupils' exploration and creativity. Preschoolers choose two or more learning areas for their free play and teacher guided activity. They could draw patterns, paint, construct, arrange materials, trace their names, tell stories and write words on paper. The teacher inspires and guide the learners; and in the process of these activities, preschoolers' literacy skills such as speaking and listening are greatly enhanced. This finding is in consonance with that of Nutbrown and Abbot (2013) which stipulates that children educated with the Reggio Emilia approach have increased tendencies for critical thinking and creativity, problem-solving abilities, cooperation and self-confidence.

Conclusion

The study investigated the effect of Reggio Emilia approach on preschoolers' academic performance in literacy skills in Akwa Ibom Northeast Senatorial District. The finding of the study reveals that there is a significant difference between the mean scores of preschoolers taught reading skills, writing skills, speaking skills and listening skills using Reggio Emilia approach and those taught using the conventional approach. Those taught literacy skills using Reggio Emilia approach had higher mean scores than their counterparts taught using the conventional approach. These results have proven that Reggio Emilia approach is an effective teaching method in enhancing preschoolers' academic performance in literacy skills.

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Recommendations

Based on the conclusion of the study and their implications, the researchers made the following recommendations:

1. Reggio Emilia approach should be adopted by teachers as a teaching method in early childhood education because it has been proven to be an effective approach in enhancing and inculcating preschoolers' literacy skills, such as reading, writing, listening and speaking.
2. The Government, through the Universal Basic Education Board, should organise seminars, workshops and training for in-service early childhood teachers to increase their awareness on the relevance of Reggio Emilia's approach, and how it can be utilised in their various schools.
3. The Government should provide funds for the provision of materials and resources in the early childhood education learning areas.
4. The Ministry of Education, through consistent inspection and monitoring, should ensure that all the schools in senatorial district with early childhood classes implements Reggio Emilia approach as an instructional strategy in early childhood care and education.

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